

Synthesis and Study of Sulphonamides from 4-(*p*-Aminophenyl)thiazoles as Possible Antimicrobial Agents

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Manuscript received 12 March 1993, revised 26 July 1993, accepted 17 September 1993

Compounds having sulphonamide group possess a variety of biological activities. Thiazole moiety has been extensively used for the preparation of newer sulphonamides¹. Also the thiazole moiety proved to have significant pharmacological properties². This prompted us of linking these two moieties to get the desired compounds which may enhance the activity against different kinds of microbes.

X = Cl; R₁ = H, CH₃;
R₂ = Aralkyl, alkyl, aryloxyalkyl etc.

Scheme 1

The required 4-(*p*-aminophenyl)-2-substituted-thiazoles HCl, 4-(*p*-aminophenyl)-5-methyl-2-substituted-thiazole HCl and 4-(*p*-amino-2'-chlorophenyl)-2-substituted-thiazole HCl were prepared according to the literature methods⁵. This was synthesised from the substituted thiobenzamides and appropriate haloketones. The required thiobenzamides were prepared⁶ from the respective benzonitriles. Various haloketones were prepared under the conditions of Friedel-Craft's reactions⁷. The acetamido benzene sulphonyl chloride was also prepared by the reported methods⁸.

The synthesis followed the sequence as depicted in Scheme 1. The haloketones, thioamides and acetamidobenzene sulphonyl chloride were synthesised following the reported methods.

Ir spectra of the compounds (6) were at the expected values^{3,4} (Table 1).

Compounds **6a**, **6i**, **6o** and **A1** showed remarkable antimicrobial activity against the three pathogens. Out of all compounds tested the four compounds have shown the good activities. The compound **6a** showed activity at 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration level against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. **6i**, **6o** and **A1** showed activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* upto 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration and **6i** showed the activity against *Echerichia coli* at 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration.

TABLE I-IR SPECTRAL DATA (CM⁻¹) OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Thiazole ring			Primary amine		Secondary amine	Alkyl group	O=S=O		1,4-Disubstituted benzene ring	
6k	1 515	1 430	1 320	3 470, 3 360	1 590	3 250	2 950	1 305	1 150	1 090	840
A1	1 520	1 435	1 330	3 460, 3 340	1 590	3 290	2 960	1 310	1 150	1 090	840
6r	1 520	1 435	1 330	3 460, 3 350	1 590	3 290	2 960, 2 920	1 310	1 160	1 090	840
6l	1 518	1 457	1 336	3 440, 3 305	1 590	3 100	2 900	1 326	1 154	1 089	830
6v	1 521	1 455	1 310	3 455, 3 300	1 592	3 190	2 965	1 310	1 153	1 091	827

Compound **6a** is capable of offering some specific antimicrobial action in chemotherapy.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of synthetic grade. Melting points were taken in an acid-bath by open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a 360 spectrometer (60 MHz).

2-Substituted-4-[(4'-aminophenyl)thiazolyl]acetyl-sulphonamide : To 4-(*p*-aminophenyl-2-phenylthiazole)hydrochloride (800 mg, 0.0031 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was added in one lot a freshly prepared anhydrous *p*-acetamidobenzene sulphonyl chloride (900 mg, 0.0044 mol). The mixture was heated over a steam-bath with intermittent stirring. When all the solid was dissolved, crushed ice (100 g) was added, stirred well and filtered. The resulting solid was purified by dissolving in 5% NaOH solution (50 ml). It was treated with charcoal and then filtered. The clear solution was acidified with HCl to precipitate the pure acetamidosulphonyl derivative⁹ (1.3 g, 94.0%; m.p. 210°).

2-Phenyl-4-(*p*-aminophenylthiazolyl)sulphonamide (6a) : To 4-(*p*-acetamidobenzene-sulphanilamido)-2-phenylthiazole (1.0 g), 5% NaOH solution was added and the mixture was heated for 0.5 h on a water-bath till a clear solution was obtained.

It was then cooled and acidified with 1 : 1 HCl in ice-water bath. The resulting solid was dried and crystallised from hexane¹⁰, (7.2 g, 79.0%), m.p. 243° (Found : C, 61.42; H, 4.50; N, 10.60. C₂₁H₁₇N₃O₂S₂ requires : C, 61.90; H, 4.10; N, 10.30%); ν_{\max} 3 470 (prim. NH₂), 3 250 (sec. NH₂), 2 950 (alkyl). 1 515 (thiazole ring), 1 150 (SO₂NH), 1 125–860 cm⁻¹ (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 2.15 (6H, ArH), 4.05 (2H, ArNH₂) 6.9–8.0 (ArH), 9.6 (1H, SO₂NHAr). Other compounds were prepared similarly from **6a–z** and **A1**, **A2** : **b** R₂ = *m*-chlorophenyl (63%), m.p. 175–76°; **c** R₂ = *o*-chlorophenyl (73%), 187°; **d** R₂ = *p*-bromophenyl (67%), 225°; **e** R₂ = 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl (56%), 222°; **f** R₂ = 3-methoxy-4-benzoyloxyphenyl (62%), 215–16°; **g** R₂ = 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl (77%), 195°; **h** R₂ = 3-ethoxy-4-benzoyloxyphenyl (70%) 199°; **i** R₂ = *p*-ethoxyphenyl (80%), 267°; **j** R₂ = *o*-tolyl (82%), 190°; **k** R₂ = *p*-tolyl (80%), 267°; **l** R₂ = *p*-propoxyphenyl (83%), 198°; **m** R₂ = 3,4,5-triethoxyphenyl (73%), 193°; **n** R₂ = 3-ethoxy-4-methoxyphenyl (67%), 220–22°; **o** R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = *m*-tolyl (78%), 141–42°; **p** R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = benzyl (73%), 210°; **q** R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = 3-methoxy-4-ethoxyphenyl (65%), 219°; **r** R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = 3,4-diethoxyphenyl (82%), 158°; **s** R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = methyl (74%), 243°; **t** R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = 5-methoxy-4-benzoyloxyphenyl (62%), 215–16°; **u** X = Cl, R₂ = 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl (75%), 159°; **v** X = Cl, R₂ = *p*-ethoxyphenyl

(86%), 398°; w R₂ = naphthoxy (70%), 225–26°; x R₂ = *p*-chlorothymoxy (69%), 170–71°; y R₂ = 2,5-dibromophenoxy (65%), 223°; z X = Cl, R₂ = 2,5-dibromophenoxy (62%), 191°; A₁ R₂ = *o*-bromo-4-methylphenoxy (72%), 185–87°; A₂ R₂ = *o*-tolylxy (68%), 183–84°.

Microbiology : Tube dilution technique¹¹ was employed for gram-positive and gram-negative organisms using Mueller-Hinton broth medium; L. J. medium was used to maintain acid-fast bacterium culture. The antitubercular activity was tested at varying concentrations in Youman's¹² liquid broth. The antimicrobial activities were evaluated against *S. aureus* (ATCC 3750), *E. coli* (ATCC 10148) and *M. tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v strain). The concentration of the compounds taken was 2 µg ml⁻¹, i.e. stock solution (pH 7.6). This stock solution was used to get final concentrations, i.e. 200, 100, 40, 20 µg ml⁻¹ in the medium during the test TR. The results were compared with the standard sulphamethoxazole and INH (0.04 µg ml⁻¹) and PAS (0.04 µg ml⁻¹). The lowest concentration of the drug showing no growth of the test organism was taken as the end-point.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. B. G. Khadse, Assistant Director, Department of Chemotherapy

for his constructive help. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. P. Bhamaria, Sr. Scientific Officer and Dr. Shrikant Athlekar for carrying out antimicrobial testing.

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